

Precision Agriculture Utilizing LoRaWAN Wireless Sensor Nodes in Greenhouses: A Case Study in Vojvodina

Abstract: This paper presents the development and deployment of wireless sensor nodes that implement Long-Range (LoRa) Wireless Area Network (WAN) to collect agricultural data relevant to the greenhouse production of vegetables in the Vojvodina region. The central part of the node is Multitech's mDot communication module based on Arm processor, and compliant with LoRaWAN communication standard. The node is capable of handling multiple sensors of different types. It supports analog, digital, and standard serial communication interfaces for sensor connection. The node is powered by a single Li-Ion or Lo-Po battery and features low power consumption. Low power is utilized inherently from LoRa infrastructure, having transmissions of data in small chunks very rarely (5 min to 1 hour or more), as well as with hardware and firmware implementation.

Keywords: Remote sensing, IoT, greenhouse production

1. Motivation

As the global population continues to expand, there is a continual rise in the demand for both food and cultivated land. According to projections from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the world population is anticipated to grow consistently at a rate of 79 million people per year, leading to an increased need for food resources [1]. A way to address this need is to increase yield and overall food production while preserving food safety and quality, as well as to reduce the impact on the environment and foster optimal usage of natural resources. One of the enablers for that is precision agriculture which relies on real-time, in-field information about the main agricultural production parameters.

2. Research questions

Greenhouse production is becoming more and more present worldwide [2] and also exhibiting uptake in the Vojvodina region of the Republic of Serbia. Greenhouse production offers numerous advantages, including an extended growing season, climate control, protection from adverse weather, increased crop yields, water efficiency, reduced pest and disease risk, optimized resource use, flexibility in crop selection, and precise control of growing conditions. This controlled environment not only ensures consistent and high-quality crop yields but also contributes to sustainability by minimizing environmental impact and supporting efficient resource management.

Greenhouse production, when integrated with sensor technologies, further enhances its efficiency and precision. Sensors play a crucial role in monitoring and controlling the growing environment by providing real-time data on factors such as temperature, humidity, light levels, soil moisture, and nutrient levels. Sensors contribute to resource efficiency by enabling precise water and nutrient management. The integration of sensors in greenhouse production not only improves crop yields but also aligns with sustainable and smart agriculture practices.

Through IoT devices and sensors, greenhouse systems can be monitored and managed remotely, allowing farmers to access real-time data on environmental conditions, crop health, and resource usage through connected devices [3]. This connectivity enables precise adjustments to climate control, irrigation, and fertilization systems based on the data received from sensors. Moreover, IoT in greenhouse production enables the use of AI algorithms, helping farmers anticipate issues and optimize crop management strategies. This interconnected approach not only enhances

efficiency and resource utilization but also supports sustainable agriculture practices by minimizing waste and improving overall yield quality.

According to [4], LoRa technology promises to have the best cost/performance trade-off IoT technology. It is expected to solve the connectivity problem of tens of billions of devices in the upcoming decade.

3. Methodology

The developed system is comprised of several components. Starting from the selection of relevant sensors for greenhouse production, development of sensor nodes, LoRa infrastructure, and finally a web-based platform for data collection, manipulation, AI algorithms implementation, and presentation in a graphical or numerical format to the user.

The selected industrial-grade sensors are based on the customer's needs and currently include a soil moisture and temperature sensor, air humidity and temperature sensor, and leaf wetness sensor. As the sensor node can accept more sensors, the list of sensors at any particular location can be extended, and tailored to the specific needs.

The sensor node is developed in-house. The hardware part consists of the main board, control and communication module, and power module, schematically represented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic presentation of the sensor node.

The main board integrates power, control and communication module, and provides necessary system connectivity. It also provides a configurable I/O interface for the connection of external sensors. The power module is a controllable two-source power supply to the sensors, providing two voltage levels to cope with the differences in required power for a broad range of sensors. The first one is for the sensors working at the voltage level of the control and communication module, while the second is a higher level voltage addressing the standard industrial sensors' voltage levels. Both power sources can be enabled or disabled over the control signals coming from the control and communication module. This feature enables significant power savings that come from the single

Li-Ion battery. The node autonomy of more than two months with a sampling rate of 30 minutes is achieved. The control and communication module is the core of the system. It is a Multitech's mDot communication module based on an Arm processor. It controls the power module, manages sensor readings, and sends collected data over the LoRaWAN to the remote server.

Fig. 2. Sensor node b) and system installed in a greenhouse.

The sensor node is shown in the left picture of Fig. 2, while the installation of one of total five nodes in the greenhouse location is shown in the right picture.

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of results coming from the sensors in AgroSense platform.

Field data coming from the sensors are uploaded to the AgroSense platform for visualization and analysis (Fig. 3).

4. Solution/Discussion

This paper presents a configurable solution for smart farming utilizing in-situ remote sensing using LoRaWAN sensor nodes integrated with the existing farm management system (AgroSense). The solution is deployed in the greenhouse production site in Kovilj, near Novi Sad, Serbia. The AgroSense is an in-house developed digital platform aimed to support farmers and agricultural companies in monitoring the growth of crops and planning agricultural activities. With its open access to the basic functionalities, it strives to attract farmers, companies, government, and other stakeholders to exploit the benefits of digitalization and smart farming solutions. Among others, it provides collection, visualization, and analysis of data from sensors deployed and associated with specific farmers/users and fields. It is important to note that reliable sensor measurement combined with data storing enabled by AgroSense represents a necessary condition for the development of AI-based decision support models, which will advise farmers in a clear and simple way on which agricultural measures should be implemented. Based on measurement results of leaf wetness, air temperature, and humidity sensors, the user of the system was able to determine if the environmental factor of the disease triangle [5] is present and whether the spraying treatment against the potential disease is needed or not. By this approach, the number of spraying treatments was cut in half compared to the conventional approach, without effect on the quality and yield.

Thanks to the utilization of the LoRaWAN network infrastructure of a mobile network provider, the cost of deployment is significantly reduced while extensive spatial coverage is provided. In addition, given the user feedback and satisfaction with the solution, physical presence, application of herbicides, and water usage are reduced while optimization and cost reduction are achieved, paving the way for sustainable agriculture and minimization of environmental impact that is expected with scaling of the solution to the whole region.

References

- [1] Jelle Bruinsma, *World Agriculture: Towards 2015/2030. An FAO perspective*, 1st ed. London: Earthscan Publications Ltd., 2003.
- [2] S. Vatari, A. Bakshi, and T. Thakur, 'Green house by using IOT and cloud computing', in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT)*, IEEE, May 2016, pp. 246–250. doi: 10.1109/RTEICT.2016.7807821.
- [3] R. Rayhana, G. Xiao, and Z. Liu, 'Internet of Things Empowered Smart Greenhouse Farming', *IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 195–211, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JRFID.2020.2984391.
- [4] Jonathan de Carvalho Silva; Joel J. P. C. Rodrigues; Antonio M. Alberti; Petar Solic; Andre L. L. Aquino, 'LoRaWAN — A low power WAN protocol for Internet of Things: A review and opportunities', in *2017 2nd International Multidisciplinary Conference on Computer and Energy Science (SpliTech)*, Split: IEEE, Jul. 2017.
- [5] George N. Agrios, *Plant Pathology*, 5th ed. San Diego: Elsevier-Academic Press, 2005.